

Real Analysis of Concurrent Height Solutions

$$\text{In[43]= Solve}\left[\sqrt{l^2 - \left(-\frac{\theta r - \gamma x}{\alpha}\right)^2} == \frac{\sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha}, \text{Reals}\right]$$

... Solve: The solution set contains a full-dimensional component; use Reduce for complete solution information.

Out[43]= { { } }

$$\text{In[44]= Reduce}\left[\sqrt{l^2 - \left(-\frac{\theta r - \gamma x}{\alpha}\right)^2} == \frac{\sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha}, \text{Reals}\right]$$

Out[44]= $\left(\theta < 0 \ \&\&$

$$\left(\left(r < \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(l == -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l == \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(l \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(r == \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& l == 0 \right) \ || \ \alpha > 0 \right) \right) \ || \left(r > \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\&$$

$$\left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(l == -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l == \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(l \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(\theta == 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\gamma < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(x < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(l == -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l == \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ || \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\&$$

$$\left(l \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ || \left(x == 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& l == 0 \right) \ || \ \alpha > 0 \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(x > 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(l == -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ || \ l == \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ || \ \left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(l \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ ||$$

$$l \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ || \left(\gamma == 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& l == 0 \right) \ || \ \alpha > 0 \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\gamma > 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(x < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\mathfrak{l} = -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \ \left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(\mathfrak{l} \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \ \left(x = 0 \ \&\& \left((\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \mathfrak{l} = 0) \ \|\| \ \alpha > 0 \right) \right) \ \|\| \\
 & \quad \left(x > 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\mathfrak{l} = -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \\
 & \quad \left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(\mathfrak{l} \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \ \left(\theta > 0 \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\left(r < \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\& \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\mathfrak{l} = -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(\mathfrak{l} \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \\
 & \quad \left(r = \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\& \left((\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \mathfrak{l} = 0) \ \|\| \ \alpha > 0 \right) \right) \ \|\| \ \left(r > \frac{x \gamma}{\theta} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \quad \left(\left(\alpha < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(\mathfrak{l} = -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\| \\
 & \quad \left(\alpha > 0 \ \&\& \left(\mathfrak{l} \leq -\sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \ \|\| \ \mathfrak{l} \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \ \|\|
 \end{aligned}$$